

Adaptation of the chlorophyll meter (SPAD) technology for real-time N management in rice: a review

V. Balasubramanian, A.C. Morales, IRRI; R.T. Cruz, Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice); T.M. Thiyagarajan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University; R. Nagarajan, M. Babu, Soil and Water Management Research Institute (SWMRI), India; S. Abdulrachman, Research Institute for Rice, Indonesia; and L.H. Hai, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MARD), Vietnam
E-mail: v.bala@cgiar.org

Blanket or package fertilizer recommendations over large areas are not efficient because indigenous nutrient supply varies widely among rice fields in Asia (Dobermann and White 1999, Olk et al 1999). Rice crops thus require different amounts of nutrients in different fields, depending on native nutrient supply and crop demand. Farmers will benefit significantly if they can adjust N inputs to actual crop conditions and nutrient requirements. The chlorophyll meter can be used to monitor plant N status *in situ* in the field and to determine the right time of N topdressing in rice (Peng et al 1996b, Balasubramanian et al 1999).

By using this tool, we can synchronize fertilizer N application with actual crop demand. This paper reviews the development and adaptation of the chlorophyll meter technique for efficient N fertilization in rice.

Chlorophyll meter

The chlorophyll meter (or SPAD meter) is a simple, portable diagnostic tool that measures the greenness or relative chlorophyll content of leaves (Inada 1963, 1985, Kariya et al 1982). Meter readings are given in Minolta Company-defined SPAD (soil plant

analysis development) values that indicate relative chlorophyll contents. There is a strong linear relationship between SPAD values and weight-based leaf N concentration (N_w), but this relationship varies with crop growth stage and/or variety (Takebe and Yoneyama 1989, Turner and Jund 1994), mostly because of leaf thickness or specific leaf weight (Peng et al 1993). The confounding effect of leaf thickness can be eliminated if foliar N concentration is expressed on a leaf-area basis. Leaf area-based N concentration (N_a) has a unique linear relationship with SPAD values of rice plants at all growth stages (Peng et al 1995).

The linear relationship between N_a and SPAD values has led to the adaptation of the SPAD meter to assess crop N status and to determine the plant's need for additional N fertilizer (Peng et al 1995, 1996b; Balasubramanian et al 1999). SPAD readings indicate that plant N status and the amount of N to be applied are determined by the physiological N requirement of crops at different growth stages. Suggested N rates for different growth stages are provided in Table 1.

Measuring SPAD values in the field

SPAD readings are taken at 7- to 10-d intervals, starting from 14 d after transplanting (DAT) for transplanted rice (TPR) and 21 d after seeding (DAS) for wet direct-seeded rice (DSR). Periodic readings continue up to the first (10%) flowering. The youngest fully expanded leaf of a plant is used for SPAD measurement. Readings are taken on one side of the midrib of the leaf blade, midway between the leaf base and tip. In early growth stages, when leaves are too narrow to allow SPAD measurements on one side of the midrib, the leaf tip can be used for measuring SPAD values. SPAD readings are more stable under the shade between 1000 and 1600 h of the day. Thus, it is recommended that SPAD readings be taken under the shade and at the same time of day, if possible. A mean of 10-15 readings per field or plot is taken as the measured SPAD value. Whenever SPAD values fall below the set critical values, N fertilizer should be applied immediately to avoid yield losses from N deficiency.

Table 1. Amount of N (kg ha⁻¹) to be applied when measured SPAD values fall below established critical values.

Growth phase	Crop duration			N (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	Short (100-115 d)	Medium (125-135 d)	Long (145-165 d)	Dry season	Wet season
<i>Transplanted rice: DAT^a</i>					
Early	14-28	14-42	14-63	30	20
Rapid	29-48	43-70	64-85	45 ^b	30 ^b
Late	49-flowering	71-flowering	86-flowering	30	20
<i>Direct-seeded rice: DAS^c</i>					
Early	21-35	21-56	21-70	30	20
Rapid	36-56	57-84	71-90	45 ^b	30 ^b
Late	57-flowering	85-flowering	91-flowering	30	20

^aDAT = d after transplanting. ^bApply the large dose of 30 kg N ha⁻¹ in the monsoon season or 45 kg N ha⁻¹ in the dry season **only once or twice maximum** during the rapid growth stage. ^cDAS = d after seeding.

SPAD threshold or critical value

The SPAD threshold or critical value indicates the leaf area-based critical N concentration (N_a) in rice leaves. Whenever SPAD readings fall below the critical value, the crop suffers from N deficiency, and yields will decline if N fertilizer is not applied immediately. For example, a SPAD threshold value of 35 is equal to 1.4–1.5 g N m⁻² of leaf area in semidwarf indica varieties (Peng et al 1996b). The SPAD threshold is not affected by luxury consumption because a plant will produce only as much chlorophyll as it needs, regardless of how much N is in the plant (Peterson et al 1993). Different SPAD threshold values are needed to optimize rice yields under different conditions (see discussion below).

Factors affecting SPAD values

Several factors affect SPAD values: radiation differences between seasons, plant density, varietal groups, nutrient status other than N in soil and plant, and biotic and abiotic stresses that induce leaf discoloration (Peterson et al 1993, Turner and Jund 1994). Users should be aware of these interfering factors and should take adequate precautions against them while using the chlorophyll meter.

Effect of radiation (season). Seasonal differences in radiation affect the SPAD critical value. For example, in the Philippines, a SPAD threshold value of 35 works well for semidwarf indica varieties in transplanted rice systems during the dry season (DS). This critical value has to be reduced to 32 for TPR during the wet season (WS) when radiation is low due to continuous, heavy cloud cover for most of the growing season (WS rice yields are less than 60% of the DS yields) (Balasubramanian et al 1999). In India, however, the critical SPAD value for TPR is 37 for the wet (kharif) season and 35–37 for the dry and winter (rabi) season to obtain high yields (IRRI-CREMNET 1998). This could be due to higher radiation in both seasons in India.

Effect of plant or tiller density. Plant density as determined by the method of crop establishment influences SPAD readings. In the Philippines, a SPAD critical value of 35 optimizes grain yields for TPR with productive tillers of 450–500 m² in the DS. When the same threshold was used for wet direct-seeded rice (W-DSR), N rates were high and grain yields were low (Balasubramanian et al 1999). Janaki and Thiyagarajan (p 24, in this issue) showed that, when the same SPAD threshold was used for various plant densities (33–100 m²) in TPR, more N was needed to produce similar grain yields in Coimbatore, India.

Under Philippine conditions, a SPAD threshold of 30 is optimum for broadcast W-DSR with around 800 productive tillers m⁻² (grain yield = 6,848 kg ha⁻¹ in 1997 DS) and 32 for row W-DSR with 650 productive tillers m⁻² (grain yield = 6,830 kg ha⁻¹ in 1997 DS) for both WS and DS (Balasubramanian et al 1998). It was observed earlier that foliar N concentration in broadcast-seeded rice was less than that of TPR at all growth stages, irrespective of amount of N applied (Peng et al 1996a). This could be due to excessive vegetative growth resulting in dilution of plant N (N-

deficient canopy) when semidwarf rice varieties developed for TPR systems are planted by broadcasting (Dingkuhn et al 1991). Thus, the critical SPAD value is inversely related to plant or tiller density. We expect that the critical SPAD values will be 30–32 for high-density (650–800 productive tillers m⁻²) and 33–35 for medium-density (400–500 productive tillers m⁻²) DSR. Further research is needed to validate the suggested critical SPAD values for direct-sown rice at different densities.

Critical SPAD values for rice varietal groups. Different threshold values may have to be used for different varietal groups (Table 2). We suggest SPAD thresholds of 30–32 for traditional or improved local and aromatic rice varieties and 35–37 for semidwarf indica varieties in the transplanted system. Tropical rice hybrids generally have thinner leaves and a slightly lower leaf N concentration than inbreds. Thus, the SPAD threshold for tropical hybrids will be equal to or slightly less than that of inbred cultivars (S. Peng, IRRI, 1999, pers. commun.). Suggested SPAD thresholds for traditional, aromatic, and hybrid rice varieties have to be confirmed by further research.

Even varieties with different grain types (coarse, medium, and fine) were shown to require different rates and patterns of N application to optimize grain yields when a single SPAD threshold value was used for all three varieties. The finer the grain type, the larger the amount of N required and the higher the number of split applications, especially after panicle initiation (Thiyagarajan and Aruna Geetha p 23, in this issue). Further research is needed to confirm whether rice varieties with different grain types require different SPAD critical values to optimize N use efficiency.

Effect of soil type and nutrient status. Phosphorus (P)-deficient rice plants produce dark green leaves that could show high SPAD values (e.g., 39, vs 35 for normal plants). Peng et al (1999) observed that SPAD values were 1-2 units higher for zero-P (P-deficient) rice plants than for P-fertilized plants at a given leaf N concentration during the vegetative phase (mid-tillering) but not at the panicle initiation stage. Thus, if the SPAD meter is used to accurately determine leaf N concentration, a different regression equation between SPAD values and leaf N concentration should be used for P-deficient and P-sufficient rice plants during the vegetative phase. Zinc and boron deficiency appears to have a minimal effect on SPAD values. SPAD readings are generally lower in peat (organic) and acid sulfate soils. Sulfur deficiency produces chlorotic leaves showing low SPAD values, and using the SPAD method for N fertilization of rice in S-deficient soils may be misleading (as we observed in Myanmar).

If the SPAD method is properly adapted to different varietal groups and crop-growing conditions and if appropriate critical SPAD values are established, this method will be highly useful for fine-tuning N fertilization of rice crops. Suggested critical values are summarized in Table 2. These values can be refined by one to two seasons of testing for locally important rice varieties and crop (environmental, nutritional, cultural) conditions.

Table 2. Suggested critical SPAD values for different seasons, cropping conditions, and rice varieties.

Crop establishment	Varietal group	Panicle density (m ⁻²)	SPAD value	
			Wet season	Dry season
Transplanted rice	Traditional, improved local, aromatic rice	300-400	30 ^a -32	32
		400-500	32 ^a -35	35 ^a -37
		400-500	32 ^a -35	35-37
Wet direct-seeded rice	All varieties	High: ~ 800	29-30 ^b	30 ^b
		Medium: ~ 400-500	32 ^a	35
		Row seeded (drum seeded)	32 ^b	32 ^b
		High: ~ 600-650	32-35	32-35
		Medium: ~ 400-500		

^aUnder Philippine conditions where radiation is low in the WVS due to continuous cloud cover for most of the growing season (mean WVS yield is less than 60% of mean DS yield).
^bValidated in the Philippines.

Cost and utility of chlorophyll meter

Because the chlorophyll meter is too expensive (US\$1,400 per unit) for farmers in developing countries, we developed a simple and inexpensive leaf color chart that can be used as an alternative decision-making tool to determine the need for N application in rice. Under practical on-farm situations, the color chart has proven to be as good as the chlorophyll meter for high grain yield and improved N use efficiency (IRRI-CREMNET 1998).

The SPAD meter, however, is highly useful as a research and training tool for researchers, extension specialists, and crop consultants. In all N-related experiments, the SPAD meter can be used to determine the N status of test crops at different growth stages for a better understanding of N dynamics in soil-plant-floodwater systems. With the chlorophyll meter, agronomists can study the N requirement of new rice varieties and develop precise N recommendations for well-defined domains. It is a quick and accurate method for breeders to evaluate segregating lines for N use efficiency, and for biotechnologists to choose N-efficient lines for identifying genes responsible for high N use efficiency. Extension specialists can verify the validity of existing N recommendations by monitoring crop N status for one to two seasons and refine them, if necessary. Extension agents and crop consultants can precisely advise clients/farmers on need-based N fertilization of rice crops after testing the N status of plants in the field. This practice will enhance the quality of the relationship and the level of confidence between the advisors and their clients.

Comparative efficiency of chlorophyll meter technique for grain yield and N use

The technical efficiency of applied N is expressed in two forms: (1) agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN), calculated as the

additional grain yield per kilogram of N applied over the control, and (2) partial factor productivity of applied N (PFP-N), calculated as the grain yield divided by the amount of N applied.

The SPAD technique is useful in measuring the current fertilizer use efficiency of farmers in different areas. Here are two examples:

- An increase in grain yield but with a higher N fertilizer use: The efficiency values are similar for the farmers' practice and the SPAD method, indicating the efficient fertilizer use by farmers as in the case of the Philippines (Table 3).
- A savings in N fertilizer use without reducing grain yield: Here grain yields are similar for both the farmers' and SPAD methods, but the amount of N used is much lower in SPAD plots compared with the farmers' practice. Therefore, efficiency values are higher for the SPAD method than for the farmers' practice or local recommendation as observed in India and Vietnam (Table 3). The farmers' N fertilization practice has to be improved.

On-farm trials have demonstrated the advantage of using the SPAD technique on rice. The increase in N use efficiency values (AEN and PFP-N) was due to higher grain yield with lesser N application in the SPAD-N plots; average savings in N fertilizer

ranged from 32 to 65 kg N ha⁻¹ for various locations in India and Vietnam (Table 3).

An inexpensive alternative to chlorophyll meter

One alternative to using the expensive chlorophyll meter is for local researchers and extension agents to use data obtained from these trials to modify local fertilizer recommendations in amounts per application and timing. A much better option is to calibrate the inexpensive leaf color chart (US\$1 per unit) with the chlorophyll meter and train farmers in its use to promote need-based N application in rice.

Research needs on chlorophyll meter method

Further research is needed to determine specific SPAD threshold values for fine-grain type, aromatic, and hybrid rice varieties. The effect of SPAD-guided N management on head rice recovery and grain quality is yet to be established.

Preliminary results of ongoing research indicate that differential rates of N application can be worked out based on observed SPAD values at critical stages of growth (early tillering, active tillering, panicle initiation, and first [10%] flowering). If these observations are confirmed, the number of SPAD measurements and split N applications will be reduced. Suggested graded levels of N application based on an observed range of SPAD values at critical crop growth stages are given in Table 4 for validation.

Researchers speculate that rice plants exposed to SPAD-regulated N supply will be healthier and less susceptible to lodging and diseases such as blast and bacterial leaf blight. We need further research to clarify the effect of need-based, SPAD-regulated N supply on plant health and plant resistance to lodging and diseases. Similarly, the effect of SPAD-guided N management on weed pressure and rice-weed competition is not understood; we require well-planned studies to assess the effect of the SPAD method of N management on the weed ecology on rice farms.

We do not use basal N application with the SPAD method. This may create problems in soils with very low soil organic matter and N contents. Removal of basal N application in such soils may reduce seedling vigor and tillering in the early growth stages. We have to develop well-defined soil criteria or indicators to distinguish soil types where basal N application will be essential in addition to SPAD-based N topdressing.

Finally, we also need to study the long-term effects of need-based N application on soil quality and soil nutrient-supplying capacity.

References

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Table 3. Comparison of chlorophyll meter (SPAD) method with farmers' practice or local recommendation for N management in rice at selected sites in various countries.^a

Treatment	N used (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN	PFP-N
<i>Philippines: Nueva Ecija, 1996 DS, 12 farms</i>				
Control	0	3.7 c	—	—
Farmers' practice	126	6.0 b	18.2	48.0
SPAD-35	150	6.7 a	19.7	44.7
<i>Philippines: Nueva Ecija, 1997 DS, 12 farms</i>				
Control	0	5.0 b	—	—
Farmers' practice	139	7.5 a	17.7 b	53.9 b
SPAD-35	138	7.2 a	15.7 b	52.2 b
UT/DP	87	7.2 a	25.3 a	83.2 a
<i>India: Old Cauvery Delta, Padugai soil series, mean of 1997 & 1998 DS</i>				
Control	0	4.9 b	—	—
Local recommendation	125	7.3 a	18.6	58.1
SPAD-35	65	7.6 a	41.2	117.2
Basal N + SPAD-35	85	7.4 a	28.4	86.5
<i>India: New Cauvery Delta, 1996 DS, 4 farms</i>				
Control	0	5.3 b	—	—
Local recommendation	125	6.4 a	8.8 b	51.6 b
SPAD-35	60	7.1 a	51.0 a	118.4 a
<i>India: New Cauvery Delta, 1998 DS, 20 farms</i>				
Control	0	3.6 b	—	—
STCR recommendation	142	5.0 a	10.3	35.4
SPAD-35	110	5.0 a	12.9	45.4
LCC-4	108	4.9 a	12.6	45.7
<i>Vietnam: Cai Lay District, 1996 WS, 6 replications</i>				
Control	0	2.8 b	—	—
Local recommendation	120	4.0 a	9.8	33.0
SPAD-32	70	4.0 a	17.8	57.5

^aAEN (agronomic efficiency of applied N) = kg additional grain over control per kg N applied. PFP-N (partial factor productivity for applied N) = grain yield divided by applied N. DS = dry season, WS = wet season. Values followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 4. Suggested graded levels of N application based on observed ranges of SPAD values at critical growth stages of semidwarf indica varieties (100-115 d) in transplanted (TPR) and direct-seeded rice (DSR) systems.*

Growth phase	TPR			DSR		
	DAT	SPAD value/ control yield	Apply N (kg ha ⁻¹)	DAS	SPAD value/ control yield	Apply N (kg ha ⁻¹)
Preplant/basal	0	Yield > 3 t ha ⁻¹ Yield < 3 t ha ⁻¹	Nil 20	0	Yield > 3 t ha ⁻¹ Yield < 3 t ha ⁻¹	Nil 20
Early tillering	14-18	SPAD > 37 SPAD 35-37 SPAD < 35	Nil 20 30	21-25	SPAD > 35 SPAD 32-35 SPAD < 32	Nil 20 30
Active tillering	28-32	SPAD > 37 SPAD 35-37 SPAD 32-34 SPAD < 32	Nil 30 40 50	35-40	SPAD > 35 SPAD 32-35 SPAD 30-31 SPAD < 30	Nil 20 30 40
Panicle initiation	42-46	SPAD > 37 SPAD 35-37 SPAD 32-34 SPAD < 32	Nil 30 40 50	50-54	SPAD > 35 SPAD 32-35 SPAD 30-31 SPAD < 30	Nil 20 30 40
First (10%) flowering	56-60	SPAD > 37 SPAD 35-37 SPAD < 35	Nil 20 30	64-68	SPAD > 35 SPAD 32-35 SPAD < 32	Nil 20 30

*Values shown are based on research conducted at different sites in Asia covered by the "Reversing Trends in Declining Productivity" project and the Crop and Resource Management Network. Further validation is ongoing.

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